

Scoping Review Protocol

Title	Evidence on Nirsevimab- and Clesrovimab immunization to prevent RSV- associated respiratory tract infections in preterm born children younger than 24 months: a scoping review protocol
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TITLE

Evidence on Nirsevimab- and Clesrovimab immunization to prevent RSV-associated respiratory tract infections in preterm born children younger than 24 months: a scoping review protocol

INTRODUCTION

Respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) is a leading cause of lower respiratory tract infection in children younger than 5 years [1]. The burden of severe disease is particularly concentrated in early infancy, with the highest hospitalization rates observed among infants aged 0–3 months [2]. In Europe, RSV accounts for an estimated 250,000 hospitalizations annually in children younger than five years, approximately 75% of which occur during the first year of life. Infants younger than two months are disproportionately affected, with hospitalization rates approaching 70 per 1,000 children in this age group [3].

Preterm infants have substantially higher risk of severe RSV disease than infants born at term for several reasons; smaller airways, immature lung and immune function, and typically lower levels of maternally derived RSV-specific IgG at birth due to shortened gestation and reduced time for transplacental antibody transfer.[4, 5] Evidence from studies conducted prior to the introduction of RSV maternal vaccination and long-acting monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) consistently demonstrates higher RSV hospitalization rates and greater need for respiratory support among preterm infants [1]. Globally, among very preterm (VPT) infants (<32 weeks gestational age) aged 0–6 months, the RSV-associated hospitalization rate is reported to be four times higher than in term infants. For moderate and late preterm infants (32–36 weeks gestation) in the same age group, the rate is about twice that of term-born infants[1]. In a Swedish population study[6], risk for ICU admissions or death in children with RSV hospitalizations were 4-fold for VPT and 6-fold for extreme preterm (< 28 weeks gestational age), compared to healthy children. Of other considered risk groups, only children with severe congenital heart disease had similar sized risk estimates in this analysis (4-fold). Furthermore, elevated risk persists into the second year of life, particularly among VPT infants[1]. Accordingly, preterm infants are therefore considered as an important target population for RSV prevention, with higher risk of severe RSV infection by lower gestational

age at birth. Gestational age should be addressed in national and international RSV immunization guidelines.

At present, no active RSV vaccine is licensed for administration directly to infants. Immunization during early infancy therefore relies on passive immunization via (1) transplacental transfer of antibodies after maternal vaccination, or (2) administration of monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) to the infant. Even with maternal vaccination, infants born prematurely or within 14 days of maternal immunization may remain insufficiently protected, making monoclonal antibodies an important complementary strategy.

MABs are preventative tools against RSV-associated disease and two mAbs are approved and in use in European countries: Palivizumab (short-acting) and Nirsevimab (extended half-life, hence long-acting). One additional long-acting mAb is available and approved in USA (FDA) with resemblance to Nirsevimab; Clesrovimab.[7] However, Clesrovimab is currently not approved in European countries as of 2025.

Nirsevimab and Clesrovimab [7] are recombinant human IgG1 kappa mAbs that bind the F1 and F2 subunits of the RSV fusion protein [8]. Nirsevimab and Clesrovimab can be administered as a single dose at birth for infants during the RSV season or shortly before the RSV seasons begin, typically October or November. Duration of protection is limited (up to 180 days), and RSV is highly seasonal. In the phase 3 MELODY trial (n=1490), Nirsevimab demonstrated 75% efficacy (95% CI 50–87) against medically attended RSV-lower respiratory tract infection (LRTI) and 62% efficacy (95% CI –9 to 87) against RSV-related hospitalization among healthy late preterm and term infants [8].

Real world post marketing data have reinforced these findings, with pooled estimates showing approximately 80% effectiveness against RSV-related emergency visits and hospitalizations, and 76% effectiveness against RSV-related ICU admissions [9].

Despite these advances, evidence specific to preterm infants remains limited. A meta-analysis by March 2025, including 7,347 preterm infants, found that Nirsevimab significantly reduced medically attended RSV-LRTI (OR = 0.25; 95% CI 0.15–0.40) and RSV-related hospitalizations (OR = 0.27; 95% CI 0.19–0.38) [10]. Of the studies included, two RCTs included gestational age down to 29 weeks of gestation. In a trial by Griffin et al. [11], 969 healthy preterm infants between 29 weeks 0 days and 34 weeks 6 days were included, 363

(37.5%) were VPT (≥ 29 - ≤ 32 weeks) and received one dose of 50 mg Nirsevimab during a 2 month period before the RSV season. By 150 days of follow up show 78 (52-90) % efficacy against severe RSV related LRTI hospitalizations, however, no specific estimate was given for the VPT group[11]. In the pragmatic HARMONIE trial[12], preterm infants born ≤ 29 weeks were included, but results include only estimates for the preterm group overall (n=1108) (OR for hospitalization-associated LRTI was 0.22 (0.07, 0.66)).

Aim

In order to identify key evidence gaps relevant for clinical decision making, policies and further research needs, the main objective of this scoping review will be to evaluate the existing evidence on Nirsevimab- and Clesrovimab immunization to prevent RSV -associated respiratory tract infections in preterm born children younger than 24 months.

METHODS AND ANALYSIS

This scoping review will be conducted in accordance with the structured framework developed by the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI). The approach aligns with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) guidelines [13]. Reporting of the findings will follow the PRISMA-ScR checklist [14]. The review process will consist of six stages: (1) formulation of the research question; (2) identification of relevant studies; (3) study selection; (4) data charting; (5) collation, summarization, and reporting of results; and (6) consultation (optional). Each stage is described in detail below. The primary literature search is planned to be conducted in February 2026. Additionally, an updated literature search will be conducted shortly before submission to capture any new studies published during the review process.

Stage 1: Identifying the research question

Preliminary searches highlight important evidence gaps regarding RSV immunization strategies with long-acting mAbs in preterm infants, particularly those born before 29 weeks' gestation. Uncertainties remain concerning efficacy, safety and dosing regimens during the first and second RSV seasons across different gestational age categories.

The following research question was formulated: What is the existing body of evidence on the use of RSV immunization with long-acting mAbs among preterm born infants younger than 24 months of age.

Stage 2: Identifying relevant studies

Relevant studies will be identified using the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) population-concept-context (PCC) framework for scoping reviews (Table 1).

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria based on the ‘population–intervention–concept–context (PICC=) Framework.

P-population	Children ≤ 24 months of age Stratified by: different gestational age groups (weeks of gestation or categories of weeks of gestation (<=28 weeks, 28-31 weeks, 32-34 weeks, 35-36 weeks, >=37 weeks, or combinations of these categories)
I-intervention	Long action immunoglobulins (Nirsevimab and Clesrovimab). Different dosing regimens
C-comparison	Immunized and non-immunized children
O-outcome	RSV associated mortality, RSV respiratory tract infection (RTI) associated intensive care treatment, RSV associated hospitalization, RSV associated RTI seeking healthcare. Reported adverse events and serious adverse events.

This scoping review will include original research articles employing quantitative designs (observational studies and randomized controlled trials (RCTs)). To be eligible for inclusion, studies must meet the following criteria: (1) publication in a peer-reviewed journal; (2) reporting of original empirical research; (3) inclusion of preterm-born (<=37 weeks) children (0-24 months of age); and (4) explicit or implicit reference to findings related to efficacy, safety and dosage of RSV immunization with long-acting mAbs.

Search strategy

The search strategy will be developed in collaboration with a medical research librarian who is a member of the research team. To identify relevant literature, a structured search strategy is designed to capture existing studies on either Nirevimab or Clesrovimab. Relevant controlled vocabulary terms and free-text synonyms (e.g., brand names or serial numbers) for the two mAb treatments will be combined using Boolean operator OR.

The search strategy will be adopted for and searched in the following bibliographic databases: MEDLINE, Embase, Cochrane Library, Web of Science and the 100 highest ranked records from Google Scholar. A preliminary search conducted in Embase.com in January 2026 retrieved a total of 938 records (Table 2). An update of the search will be performed in the listed databases prior to publication to ensure that any newly published studies are also included.

Table 2. Preliminary search strategy applied in Embase.com.

Row	Search terms/query
1.	'nirsevimab'/exp
2.	'clesrovimab'/exp
3.	'nirsevimab':ti,ab,kw
4.	'beyfortus':ti,ab,kw
5.	'medi 8897':ti,ab,kw
6.	'medi8897':ti,ab,kw
7.	'sp 0232':ti,ab,kw
8.	'sp 232':ti,ab,kw
9.	'sp0232':ti,ab,kw
10.	'sp232':ti,ab,kw
11.	'clesrovimab':ti,ab,kw
12.	'enflonsia':ti,ab,kw
13.	'mk 1654':ti,ab,kw
14.	'mk1654':ti,ab,kw
15.	#1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12 OR #13 OR #14

Abbreviations: Exploded thesaurus term (exp/). Title, abstract and author keywords (:ti,ab,kw).

Stage 3: Selection of relevant studies

References retrieved from the selected databases will be exported to EndNote (Clarivate Analytics), where duplicate records will be identified and removed. The remaining unique records will be imported to Covidence (Covidence systematic review software, Veritas Health Innovation, Melbourne, Australia. Available at www.covidence.org) for screening. Two

members of the research team will independently screen titles and abstracts according to the predefined eligibility criteria. The team includes researchers with clinical expertise and experience in health services research. Screening decisions will be blinded, meaning that reviewers will not be aware of other reviewers' eligibility assessment. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion and consensus, or, if necessary, by consultation with an additional team member. Throughout the screening process, Covidence will automatically generate a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) flow chart.

Stage 4: Charting the data

Eligible studies meeting the inclusion criteria will be charted in an evidence table that will be continuously updated by all reviewers conducting full-text assessments. The initial structure of the data chart will be generated using Covidence's export functions. For original research articles, the following data items will be extracted: author(s); year of publication; country of origin (where the study was conducted or published); study aims or objectives; study population and sample size; methodology; outcomes and outcome measures; and key findings relevant to the scoping review questions (e.g., laboratory -confirmed infection, hospitalization, and disease-specific mortality). Effect measures will include vaccine effectiveness estimate, risk ratios, and odds ratios with corresponding 95% confidence interval. Planned subgroup assessments include gestational age groups and ages at intervention (newborn, infants in first RSV season, children in second RSV season). Data on safety and dosing will be extracted and presented when documented in the included studies.

Data extraction will be conducted by the research team using Covidence. To ensure the data charting framework is fit for purpose, a pilot test will be performed using a sample of five original research articles. The data items will be refined as necessary based on this pilot. If necessary, we will add or remove data items accordingly.

Stage 5: Collating, summarizing and reporting the results

Reporting will adhere to the PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) checklist. Key quantitative characteristics, such as country of origin, year of publication, study population, study design, and type timing of the vaccine/immunization will be reported.

This approach will allow identification of key gaps in the existing literature on RSV immunization in preterm infants and may inform future research directions.

The review will not include quantitative assessment of study quality or risk of bias.

Stage 6: Consultation

During the later part of Stage 5, a consultation workshop will be conducted with members of the IMPROVE Preterm team and the project's relevant expert. This workshop will provide additional perspectives that can enhance the quality, relevance, and overall usefulness of the review.

ETHICS AND DISSEMINATION

This scoping review will synthesize evidence from publicly available sources and will not involve primary data collection or interaction with human participants. Therefore, formal ethical approval is not required. This review forms part of the project *IMPROVing lifElong health and development for children and adults born very PRETERM – observational studies to enhance randomized trials for comparative effectiveness research (IMPROVE PRETERM)*. Findings will be disseminated in a peer-reviewed journal. Open access will be ensured.

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11. Griffin, M.P., et al., *Single-Dose Nirsevimab for Prevention of RSV in Preterm Infants*. *N Engl J Med*, 2020. **383**(5): p. 415–425.
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13. Peters, M.D.J., et al., *Updated methodological guidance for the conduct of scoping reviews*. *JBI Evid Synth*, 2020. **18**(10): p. 2119–2126.
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Annexes

PRISMA-ScR Checklist

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a scoping review.	0
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary that includes (as applicable): background, objectives, eligibility criteria, sources of evidence, charting methods, results, and conclusions that relate to the review questions and objectives.	0
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known. Explain why the review questions/objectives lend themselves to a scoping review approach.	0
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the questions and objectives being addressed with reference to their key elements (e.g., population or participants, concepts, and context) or other relevant key elements used to conceptualize the review questions and/or objectives.	0
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web address); and if available, provide registration information, including the registration number.	0
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.	0
Information sources*	7	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.	0
Search	8	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least 1 database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	0
Selection of sources of evidence†	9	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.	0
Data charting process‡	10	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms that have been tested by the team before their use, and whether data charting was done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	0
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.	0
Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence§	12	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	0
Synthesis of results	13	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.	0

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
RESULTS			
Selection of sources of evidence	14	Give numbers of sources of evidence screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally using a flow diagram.	0
Characteristics of sources of evidence	15	For each source of evidence, present characteristics for which data were charted and provide the citations.	0
Critical appraisal within sources of evidence	16	If done, present data on critical appraisal of included sources of evidence (see item 12).	0
Results of individual sources of evidence	17	For each included source of evidence, present the relevant data that were charted that relate to the review questions and objectives.	0
Synthesis of results	18	Summarize and/or present the charting results as they relate to the review questions and objectives.	0
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	19	Summarize the main results (including an overview of concepts, themes, and types of evidence available), link to the review questions and objectives, and consider the relevance to key groups.	0
Limitations	20	Discuss the limitations of the scoping review process.	0
Conclusions	21	Provide a general interpretation of the results with respect to the review questions and objectives, as well as potential implications and/or next steps.	0
FUNDING			
Funding	22	Describe sources of funding for the included sources of evidence, as well as sources of funding for the scoping review. Describe the role of the funders of the scoping review.	0

From: Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Ann Intern Med.* 2018;169:467–473. doi: [10.7326/M18-0850](https://doi.org/10.7326/M18-0850).